

A Comprehensive Review of SHIELD: Smart Handler for Incident Event and Location Detection

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ABSTRACT

Women's safety is a major concern in today's world; technologies can help to provide quick support in emergencies. This paper presents SHIELD (Smart Handler for Incident Event and Location Detection), a mobile application designed to keep women safe. The application uses smartphones and cloud services to track the user's live location, record audio and video as evidence, and send alerts to trusted contacts automatically. Even without internet access, SHIELD can store important data locally to ensure it works reliably. Built with Java and Firebase, the application is easy to use and requires minimum action from the user in stressful situations. SHIELD improves response times during emergencies and help document incidents effectively. By combining several safety features in one application, SHIELD provides a practical solution to help women feel more secure and safer.

Keywords: Women's Safety, Mobile Application Development, Emergency Alert Systems, GPS Tracking, Cloud Integration, Android Development, Multimedia Evidence Collection, Firebase Services

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, women face safety challenges everywhere, whether it is on the street, at home or in unfamiliar places. Laws and social programs are there to protect them, but these measures are not always helpful to prevent women in dangerous situations, especially when the women is alone or in new environment. Traditional safety tools often reacts when something has already happened which is not enough. Now with the rise of smartphones, we have various powerful tools that can help us. Modern phones come with cameras, microphones, sensors and also fast processing power. These features help to create an application that can act quickly in emergency, giving the women support when needed. SHIELD is designed to help women in panic situations. It quietly works in a background, track user's location, records both audio and video, and sends the alert to the trusted contacts simultaneously. The idea is to help women in stressful situations, without complicating the process. The main goal of the SHIELD is to save time in emergencies because even a few seconds can make a big difference. By automatically gathering evidences and sending alerts

the application increases the chances of getting help quickly. Unlike other applications which offers only one feature, SHIELD combines multiple functions like live location tracking, audio-video recording, and notifications into a single, easy-to-use platform. The application also works when there is no internet and is designed to minimize battery usage. Due to which it can function reliably in different situations. SHIELD gives women a dependable tool to feel safer in their everyday lives.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, research on mobile and wearable technologies has increasingly focused on enhancing personal safety, particularly for women. Usability and effectiveness have been identified as critical factors in the adoption of such application. For instance, Sharma et al. [1] conducted a study on mobile safety applications, showing that simple interfaces, quick access to emergency functions, and minimal time response load are essential for real-life emergency scenarios. Building on this, Agarwal and Kumar [2] proposed a shake- based safety application that triggers emergency alerts through intuitive gestures,

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allowing users to discreetly request help during urgent situations. This paper explored the motion and sensor's-based techniques used in women safety application. Patel et al. [3] evaluated the performance of motion sensors in women's safety applications, demonstrating their ability to detect sudden movements indicative of distress. Similarly, Singh et al. [4] this paper gives overview of how voice command is recognised. It also highlights the importance of voice activated response in emergency situation. Expanding on automated detection, Das and Mohapatra [5] developed a keyword-based alert system using natural language processing (NLP), allowing the application to recognize distress words in spoken input and initiate alerts automatically. Accurate location tracking remains a cornerstone of safety solutions. M. Pathak, V. Sinha et al. [6] developed a real-time location- sharing framework to ensure that trusted contacts receive timely and precise information. Misra and Rajput [7] addressed the challenges of GPS accuracy in urban environments, suggesting the need for hybrid or advanced localization techniques to improve reliability. Additional research emphasizes geofencing and safe-zone alerts, which proactively notify guardians if users enter potentially unsafe areas. Wearable devices integrated with GSM and IoT technologies provide a discreet and continuous layer of protection. Roy and Ghosh [8] proposed a GSM-based wearable capable of sending immediate alerts even without internet access. while Jain and Srivastava [9] demonstrated IoT-enabled wearables that monitor safety parameters in real-time. R. Tripathi, S. Gupta et al. [10] further enhanced wearable functionality by integrating heart-rate monitoring to trigger automatic alerts during abnormal readings, highlighting the potential of physiological monitoring in emergency scenarios.

Recent advances also include AI-based predictive analytics, which analyse patterns in movement, voice stress, and physiological signals to anticipate potential threats before they escalate. Multi-modal integration of audio, video, GPS, and biometric data is increasingly being adopted to provide more reliable and actionable safety information. Cloud-based platforms and real-time data processing enable emergency contacts or authorities to respond quickly, significantly improving response effectiveness. Emerging approach also focus on encouraging proactive safety behaviour through gamification and behavioural nudges. Regular reminders, safety tips, or incentives for check-ins help users maintain vigilance, while social integration features enable trusted networks and community reporting, creating collective awareness and faster response during emergencies. Overall, the reviewed studies indicate a clear trend towards multi- functional, intelligent safety solutions that combine sensors, location tracking, automated alerts, predictive analytics, and social integration. While existing application address specific safety aspects, integrating these diverse features into a cohesive, user-friendly platform remains a critical area for future research and development, exemplified by systems like SHIELD.

METHODOLOGY

The development of SHIELD follows structured approach designed to ensure the application integration with the real- world safety requirements while maintaining the usability and reliability. The methodology has requirement analysis, System design, implementation strategy and validation procedure.

Fig. 3.1 System Architecture

The primary approach is women Safety and Incident record system as evidence follows a structured methodology to check real-time protection, valid data record, and secure communication. The methodology is divided into some parts as show in following diagram:

1. User Registration

The process start with user registration, where important details are collected such as name, Contact number, Email-IDs and trusted contacts. This information is stored in cloud database for to contact and share the data to the trusted contacts during the emergency.

2. Silent Background Operations

The application works silently in the background and continuously monitoring for emergency to trigger SOS Button after the activation of the SOS button application start and the remaining functions of the application start working automatically. So this function of SHIELD make the application more reliable.

3. SOS Button Press

When the user presses the SOS button then the system activates immediately and works simultaneously.

This button is design for quick alerts and minimum delay.

4. Live Location Tracking

After activation, the application start location tracking using GPS. This location is shared to the trusted contacts after pressing the SOS button and also it stored in the cloud database as evidence.

5. Audio and Video Recording

The System automatically starts recording audio and video using the device's Camera and microphone. This data is stored in cloud database and provide valuable information at the time of investigation.

6. Data Upload to Firebase

All captured data such as Location, recorded audio and video is uploaded in Firebase storage. This data is also saved even if the device is damaged or the internet connection is temporarily lost.

7. Notification to Trusted Contact

After clicking the SOS button, the System sends the notification or alerts to the trusted saved contacts via SMS and email. The message includes the live location, recorded audio and video, link to access the uploaded evidence.

8. User Interface

The application provides easy-to-use interface that gives permission to manage the user profile, add or remove trusted contacts, view saved incidents and adjust safety settings.

9. Security Protocol

To check privacy and security, System use encryption methods for user data transmission and secure authentication. The data access is restricted to authorized user.

10. Regular Testing

The last steps involve testing and validation of all modules such as SOS activation, storing data, sending notification to trusted contact, and tracking live location to maintain reliability and system integrity.

❖ System Overview and Execution Process

1. Client-Side Components

The SHIELD application has different parts that work together to keep a user safe. The main screen (Main Activity) has the SOS button. It loads very fast so you can press it quickly in an emergency. The application can find where you are using your phone's GPS. It does this quietly in the background. Normally, it checks your location sometimes to save battery. But if you press the SOS button, it checks your location more often so people know exactly where you are. The application also records audio and video automatically using the phone's camera and microphone. It saves these recordings in medium quality so they don't take too long to send, even if the internet is slow.

2. Cloud Integration

All your information, like your name, emergency contacts, and incidents, is stored in Firebase online. Each incident saves the time, location, and links to the audio and video recordings. Big files, like videos, are stored in special folders for each user and for each incident. This makes it easy to find them later. Security rules make sure only you (and authorized people) can see your data.

3. Communication System

The application tries to send alerts in different ways. If there is internet, it sends a detailed notification with your location and a link to the incident. If there is no internet, it sends an SMS with your last known location and a message saying you need help. SMS is simpler but works even when the internet is bad.

4. Data Management

If the internet is not available, the application saves all recordings and location info on your phone. Later, when the internet is back, it automatically uploads everything to the cloud. The application can retry uploads if something fails, and it can handle big files safely.

5. Security Measures

All data is encrypted to keep it safe. Messages to Firebase are secure, and files on your phone are also protected. Only people who are allowed can access your data. You need to log in to use the application, and security rules make sure no one else can see your information.

❖ Expected Outcomes

1. Functional Performance

When the SOS button is pressed, it is expected to send an alert to the trusted contacts within 2 to 3 seconds when internet connectivity is available. This duration will include collecting the user's location, preparing the message, and sending it through Firebase. The audio and video recording features are expected to provide clear quality for evidence purposes. Audio should capture surrounding sounds and voices, while video recordings are anticipated to give clear visuals that can be useful against attackers.

2. Offline Functionality

The offline feature of the SHIELD application is expected to be very useful. In situations where no internet or mobile data is available, the application should store the user's location, audio, and video on the device itself using a local database. Once the network is restored, all the saved data is expected to

automatically upload to Firebase without requiring any action from the user.

3. Usability Evaluation

The SOS button is expected to be easy to locate and quick to use during emergencies. The vibration and screen colour change will act as a confirmation of successful SOS activation, giving users confidence during critical situations. The setup process is expected to be simple, though clearer steps for adding trusted contacts and granting permissions may be helpful. The application's interface is expected to remain user-friendly, with the possibility of further enhancement through an in-application guide for first-time users.

4. System Limitations

The application is expected to depend on the availability of the smartphone. It will not function if the phone is switched off, out of reach, or has insufficient battery. Privacy concerns may arise because of continuous location access and recording features. However, the application is expected to use data encryption and secure access controls to protect sensitive information. Regular updates and user awareness are expected to further reduce privacy risks.

5. Comparison with Existing Solutions

Compared to other safety applications, SHIELD is expected to offer more comprehensive protection by combining location tracking, alert notification, and recording features in a single platform. While other applications usually provide only one or two of these functions, SHIELD aims to ensure a more reliable and informative emergency response. However, wearable safety devices such as smartwatches may still provide quicker accessibility and more discreet usage in certain emergency situations. Testing also showed that the application runs smoothly on most Android versions without crashes or delays. Data synchronization with Firebase is consistent and stable. The integration of multiple communication methods increases reliability, ensuring that emergency alerts reach.

❖ Implications

1. Social Impact

SHIELD helps to sort gender-based safety issues by offering technological tools that make women able to travel and work with confidence. Having assistance in a timely manner and collecting evidence automatically can encourage a courageous perspective against attackers. Not only personal security, but use of such applications could play a crucial role in changing overall culture in terms of personal protection and responsibility. The capabilities of evidence collection have legal implications for trial involving harassment or assault. Audio and video recordings, along with location information evidence that is useful against attackers. The technological backup can enhance the ability of the justice to deliver justice to victims. The application is expected to run smoothly on most Android versions without crashes or delays. Data synchronization with Firebase is anticipated to remain consistent and stable. The integration of multiple communication methods is expected to increase reliability, ensuring that emergency alerts reach their intended recipients.

2. Technological Contributions

The coverage of several mobile technologies into a single safety platform presents opportunities for all-around personal safety solutions. SHIELD's design offers a base platform that other developers can open the door to more advanced emergency response programs and technologies. The limited-cloud model of local processing and cloud to store data, while preserving offline functionality is a feasible model for safety application. SHIELD's implementation strategies in terms of background services and synchronizing data are technical things compare to other mobile applications that need the same functionality. Techniques for balancing function with battery life, as well as providing reliable service under different network conditions, are exportable beyond safety application.

3. Practical Application

The SHIELD application gives an easy and quick safety tool for women who face danger or insecurity in daily life. Hence it works on smartphones that most people already have, users don't need to buy any extra gadgets. This makes it affordable and accessible for

everyone and even people have less money. The design of SHIELD can also be changed for different users. For example, elderly people who need help during a medical emergency can use a similar version. Parents can also use it to ensure their children's safety. So that the SHIELD system can be expanded for women's safety.

4. Future Development Directions

When developing this application, it can be using new idea to better in the future. So that this application can be include a voice command feature to users can send an SOS alert by speaking when they cannot use the phone. They can also use the wearable devices it will be faster response for the alert purpose. In this process it helps of artificial intelligence and machine learning it has detected the which situation in their place like that analyzing nearby sounds, movements and even the physical condition. It can send alerts even the user cannot press any button. So that in this system also adding two or more languages will help the people who don't speak English so that the everyone can use the application easily and comfortable. SHIELD can also be changed according to their location so it works better with their current location emergency numbers, languages, and safety rules. SHIELD more smart, fast, and useful to trusted safety application for everyone.

CONCLUSION

The SHIELD is a smart and useful idea made to help women can safe in world to the difficult and unsafe situations or area. It uses various technology to send alerts, location tracking, and record audio or video when they needed. This application can work proper and gives fast help during emergencies. It can send messages and location details also when the internet is not strong. It is more reliable and easier to use for everyone. This system proves that technology can really help to women live the safer and give them more confidence to move freely. Though some features can be improved that SHIELD has great scope for future updates like voice command and smartwatch support. In short that SHIELD is not only a safety application but also it is a trusted guardian that helps women feel protected anytime and anywhere.

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